

Selective electrochemical detection of ascorbic acid in canned juice using aniline/*N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylene-diamine modified MWCNT electrode

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Abstract : Selective electrochemical detection of ascorbic acid (AA) in fruit juice is an important analytical problem. Since electrochemical techniques offer an easy extension to portable device, design and development of new chemically modified electrodes, which can able to sense AA is most wanted in quick quality control assessment. Herein we report, an electro-copolymerized aniline/*N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylene-diamine (NED) on MWCNT modified gold electrode (Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED) in a neutral pH solution for highly efficient and low potential detection of AA in canned fruit juice. The NED acts as a linker to improve the stability of the polyaniline/MWCNT composite in neutral pH. The electrochemical sensor showed AA oxidation peak at low potential, -15 mV vs Ag/AgCl in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution. The Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED was characterized by cyclic voltammetry, Raman, FT-IR and UV-Vis spectroscopy techniques. Under optimal amperometric *i-t* condition, Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED showed AA calibration plot in a window 200–2000 μM with a current sensitivity of 13.45 nA μM^{-1} . A canned fruit juice real sample was successfully analyzed with recovery value $\sim 100\%$.

Keywords : Ascorbic acid, electrocatalysis, co-polymer, polyaniline.

Introduction

Ascorbic acid (AA) is an important antioxidant that plays a vital role in human physiological systems¹. Fruits and vegetables like, grapes, oranges, broccoli and spinach are rich source of AA². Vitamin tablets and canned fruit juices are alternatives. Dependence on the storage period the amount of AA in the canned fruit juices may vary. For instance, storage of commercial fruit juices in closed containers at room temperature for 4 months resulted in about 30–40% loss of AA activity³. Thus, development of a sensitive and simple method for the rapid assessment of AA in the canned fruit juices is highly desirable for strict quality control. There are several analytical methods like titration, fluorimetry, chemiluminescence and electrochemical methods reported for AA detection⁴. Amongst them, electrochemical method is considered to be the best for AA detection. Unfortunately, unmodified bulk carbon electrodes like glassy carbon electrode (GCE), carbon paste electrodes suffered for serious surface fouling and large over-potential⁵. To avoid these, several chemically modified electrodes (CME) are developed. For example, polyvinyl pyridine (PVP)-Mo(CN)₆³⁻-

CME⁶, 1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione/carbon nanotube (CNT)-CME⁷ and polyaniline (PANI)/polyacrylic acid/multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT)/Nafion(Nf)/Pt-CME for AA electrochemical detection. However, their usability in neutral pH is limited. It could be noted, AA detection by PVP-Mo(CN)₆³⁻ in 0.1 M H₂SO₄ showed $\sim 20\%$ loss in sensitivity⁶. In our recent publication, we have reported successful preparation of PANI/MWCNT composite CME unusually in a neutral pH solution⁹. In this work, an aniline/*N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylene-diamine (NED) copolymer-MWCNT modified gold electrode (Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED) is prepared and utilized for efficient electro-catalytic oxidation of AA and sensitive amperometric detection of AA in a canned fruit juice.

Experimental

Materials and reagents : MWCNTs (> 90% carbon basis, outer diameter : 10–15 nm; inner diameter : 2–6 nm; length 0.1–10 μm) obtained from Aldrich, USA. Ascorbic acid, aniline and *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylene-diamine dihydrochloride reagents purchased from Rankem, Sd-fine chemicals, CDH respectively were used without further purification. Aqueous solutions were prepared using

deionized and alkaline KMnO_4 double distilled (DD) water. Unless otherwise stated pH 7 PBS of 0.1 M ionic strength was used as a supporting electrolyte.

Apparatus and characterization : All voltammetric measurements were carried out using CHI 660C electrochemical work station, USA with 10 mL working volume. The three electrode system consists of gold (Au) electrode of 0.0414 cm^2 geometrical surface area and its chemically modified electrode as a working electrode, Pt wire as a counter and Ag/AgCl was used as a reference electrode. The bio-analytical system (BAS, USA) polishing kit was used to polish the Au surface. Raman spectra were recorded using Peakseeker Pro Raman Spectrometer (Agiltron, USA) using 532 nm laser probe. Fourier transform-infrared (FT-IR) spectra ($4000\text{--}400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) measurements were done using IR affinity⁻¹ FT-IR spectrometer (Shimadzu, Japan) as KBr pellet. A V-670 spectrometer (JASCO, Japan) was used for the UV-Vis measurements.

Preparation of chemically modified electrodes : Prior to the modification, the Au surface was cleaned both mechanically (polished with 1μ alumina powder in the BAS polishing kit, cleaned with acetone and followed by DD water) and electrochemically by performing CV for ten cycles in the potential window -0.2 V to 1.2 V in pH 7 PBS at scan rate (ν) 50 mV s^{-1} ($n=10$, n = no. of cycles). Then $5 \mu\text{L}$ of MWCNT of 1 mg MWCNT dispersed in $500 \mu\text{L}$ ethanol was drop-casted on bare Au and kept for drying in room temperature for 2 min. The Au/MWCNT was then pretreated electrochemically by performing continuous CV at $\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ in the blank pH 7 PBS in the potential window of -0.5 to 0.5 V ($n = 10$). Au/MWCNT@PANI and Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED were prepared by continuous potential cycling of the Au/MWCNT in a freshly prepared aniline solution ($50 \mu\text{L}$ aniline + $450 \mu\text{L}$ ethanol + 9.5 mL of pH 7 PBS) and aniline + NED solution ($50 \mu\text{L}$ aniline + 2 mg of NED + $900 \mu\text{L}$ ethanol + 9 mL of pH 7 PBS) in a potential window -0.5 to 0.5 V at $\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ ($n = 10$) respectively. As prepared chemically modified electrodes were electrochemically pretreated in a potential window of -0.5 to 0.5 V in pH 7 PBS at $\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$ ($n = 10$).

Real sample : Tropicana grape fruit juice was purchased from local market and stored in refrigerator until it use. Prior to analysis, fruit juice was filtered using syringe filters and used without any dilution.

Results and discussion

Fig. 1A is a ten continuous potential cycling of a pristine MWCNT modified gold electrode (Au/MWCNT) in 50 mM of aniline and 1.25 mM of NED dissolved in pH 7 phosphate buffer solution (PBS). As can be seen a continuous growth of redox peaks at A1/C1, A2/C2 and A3/C3 corresponds to leucoemeraldine/emeraldine (A1/C1) and emeraldine/pernigraniline (A3/C3)¹⁰ and NED's (A2/C2) redox transitions were observed. Repeated experiments with unmodified Au failed to show any such polymer formation (data not enclosed). This particular experiment evidenced the key role of MWCNT for the PANI redox activity⁹. Fig. 1B displays the electrochemical response of Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED (curve a) in pH 7 with comparative electrochemical behaviors of Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED (curve b), Au/MWCNT@PANI (curve c), Au/MWCNT (curve d) and Au (curve e) for the AA oxidation in pH 7 solution. As can be seen the optimal working electrode, i.e. Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED showed the highest AA oxidation current signal and with low oxidation potential over the other unmodified electrodes. This observation implies efficient electro-catalytic feature of the optimal electrode in this work. Meanwhile, the AA oxidation of the Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED (Fig. 1B, curve b) is compared with Au/MWCNT@PANI (Fig. 1B, curve c). Interestingly, quantitatively similar electrocatalytic response was noticed. Only advantage with the co-polymeric PANI-NED/MWCNT system is stability. Ten continuous CV responses of Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED in pH 7 PBS displayed a relative standard deviation (RSD) value 1.4%; while the Au/MWCNT@PANI showed a value of 10% (data not enclosed).

Fig. 1. (A) Continuous CV responses of Au/MWCNT in pH 7 aniline and NED solution at $\nu = 50 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$. (B) CV responses of Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED without (curve a) and with (curve b) 5 mM AA, and Au/MWCNT@PANI, Au/MWCNT and Au with 5 mM AA (curve c, d and e) at $\nu = 10 \text{ mV s}^{-1}$.

To find the molecular level details of Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED, the composite electrode is subjected to various physicochemical characterizations viz. Raman, FT-IR and UV-Vis spectroscopic techniques. Fig. 2A represents Raman spectra of Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED in comparison with Au/MWCNT@PANI and Au/MWCNT samples. Calculated intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) of D band (I_D) and G band (I_G), where the G band is due to pure graphite structure with sp^2 carbon and the D band is a disorder mode due to oxygen functionalities with sp^3 carbon unit, are 0.29, 0.35 and 0.53 respectively. The decrement in the I_D/I_G ratio upon PANI-NED modification on MWCNT indicates formation of several conjugated structures (conducting polymer) with sp^2 bonding on the surface of the MWCNT⁹. Fig. 2B displays comparative FT-IR responses of MWCNT@PANI-NED and MWCNT@PANI. Appreciable peaks corresponding to the quinonoid ($-C=N-$, 1617 cm^{-1}), benzenoid ($-C=C-$, 1456 cm^{-1}) and aromatic hydrogen ($-C-H$, 1154 cm^{-1}) groups¹¹ were noticed. This observation is similar to the case of Au/MWCNT@PANI system⁹. UV-Vis characterization (Fig. 2C) showed significant negative shift in the absorption spectra with the optimal system ($\lambda = 329$) over the MWCNT@PANI ($\lambda = 314$). Presumably, there may be strong interaction between the co-polymer and MWCNT and hence significant shift in the UV-Vis absorption signal. Overall, structure of Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED closely resembles with Au/MWCNT@PANI except the stability in neutral pH solution.

Fig. 3A displays amperometric $i-t$ responses of Au,

Au/MWCNT, Au/MWCNT@PANI, Au/MWCNT@NED and Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED for sensing of $200\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ spikes of AA in 10 mL pH 7 PBS at a fixed applied potential -15 mV vs Ag/AgCl under hydrodynamic condition (RPM ~ 700). It is obvious that the unmodified electrodes, Au and Au/MWCNT (Fig. 3A, curves a and b) showed either nil or feeble current responses for the AA sensing, whereas Au/MWCNT@PANI (curve c) and Au/MWCNT@NED (curve d) yielded appreciable current signals. It can be noted that the Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED (curve e) showed the highest current value for the AA over the other electrodes. Inset Fig. 3a, is a calibration plot for the AA sensing on the optimal system. A linear line with sensitivity and regression coefficient (R) values $13.46\text{ }\mu\text{A }\mu\text{M}^{-1}$ and 0.985 respectively were noticed. Six continuous spikes of $200\text{ }\mu\text{M}$ AA displayed a RSD 0.33% . Calculated detection limit, D_L (signal-to-noise = 3) value is $76.27\text{ }\mu\text{M}$. The optimal electrode showed tolerable interference to nitrite (NO_2^-), cysteine (CySH), uric acid (UA), dopamine (DA), glucose (Glu) and citric acid (Cit) (Fig. 3B). Finally using this method, content of AA in a canned fruit juice was tested by standard addition approach (Fig. 3C). Inset Fig. 3b is plot of current (μA) vs [AA] for the real sample. Observed linear equation for the plot is $i(y) = 0.007836(x) + 1.628$ ($R = 0.999$). From the electro-analysis AA content value 75 mg per 100 mL was calculated. Unfortunately, there is no detail of the amount of AA on the canned fruit juice label to compare the calculated value! Overall, the new electrode developed in this work is highly suitable for AA content analysis in fruit juices.

Fig. 2. (A) Raman spectra of Au/MWCNT before and after modification with PANI and PANI-NED, (B) FT-IR of MWCNT@PANI and MWCNT@PANI-NED and (C) UV-Vis responses of ethanol extract of MWCNT@PANI-NED and MWCNT@PANI along with control MWCNT + ethanol and aniline samples.

Fig. 3. (A) Amperometric $i-t$ responses of Au (a), Au/MWCNT (b), Au/MWCNT@PANI (c), Au/MWCNT@NED (d) and Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED with continuous spikes of $200 \mu\text{M}$ of AA in pH 7 PBS. (B) Effect of interference like NO_2^- , CySH, UA, DA, Glu and Cit on Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED. (C) Real sample analysis using Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED by standard addition approach ($S = 200 \mu\text{M}$). Inset a and b are the corresponding plots of [AA] vs current. Optimal conditions : applied potential = -15 mV vs Ag/AgCl, rpm = 700.

Conclusions

Electro-copolymerized aniline/*N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine (NED) on MWCNT modified gold electrode (Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED) in a neutral pH solution showed highly efficient electrocatalytic oxidation of AA in a pH 7 PBS. Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED was characterized by Raman, FT-IR and UV-Vis spectroscopies. The results revealed no major difference in structural and electrochemical behavior of the Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED with Au/MWCNT@PANI, except stability. The Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED showed the highest amperometric $i-t$ response to AA over the other unmodified electrodes viz. Au/MWCNT@PANI, Au/MWCNT@NED, Au/MWCNT and Au. Applicability of the Au/MWCNT@PANI-NED for sensitive sensing of AA in a canned fruit juice was successfully demonstrated with a recovery value $\sim 100\%$. This technique can be extended to test AA in several other real samples.

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